

Net Neutrality: A Debate in Current Scenario

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Abstract:

Net Neutrality is very important in every field like entrepreneurs, business hubs, education sector, banking sector. They can do their related activities through internet. Marketing is done online and products are sold openly, without any discrimination. It will generate the opportunity of employment. All big companies are growing rapidly through net neutrality. Thus lack of net neutrality may become a barrier in growth of these large sector using the internet for their business. Also freedom of speech is highly related to net neutrality. One can put their voice publically, express their views in public domain. Net neutrality facilitate all these. It will mean Internet Service Providers (ISP) will be able to charge companies like YouTube or yahoo as they require more bandwidth, and eventually the load of the extra amount will be pushed to the consumers. Moreover, ISPs can then create slow as well as fast Internet lanes, which will mean all websites cannot be accessed at the same speed and one can do so only on paying an additional sum.

Keywords: Internet Neutrality, Service providers, communication, ISP and TRAI

1. Introduction

The principle that Internet service providers should enable access to all content and applications regardless of the source, and without favoring or blocking particular products or websites is now known as Net Neutrality.

Net neutrality is an idea derived from how telephone lines have worked since the beginning of the 20th century. In case of a telephone line, you can dial any number and connect to it. It does not matter if you are calling from operator A to operator B. It doesn't matter if you are calling a restaurant or a drug dealer. The operators neither block the access to a number nor deliberately delay connection to a particular number, unless forced by the law. Most of the countries have rules that ask telecom operators to provide an unfiltered and unrestricted phone service.

When the internet started to take off in 1980s and 1990s, there were no specific rules that asked that internet service providers (ISPs) should follow the same principle. But, mostly because telecom operators were also ISPs, they adhered to the same principle. This principle is known as net neutrality. An ISP does not control the traffic that passes its servers. When a web user connects to a website or web service, he or she gets the same speed. Data rate for Youtube videos and Facebook photos is theoretically same. Users can access any legal website or web service without any interference from an ISP.

Some countries have rules that enforce net neutrality but most don't. Instead, the principle is followed because that is how it has always been. It is more of a norm than a law.

There are no laws enforcing net neutrality in India. Although TRAI guidelines for the Unified Access Service license promotes net neutrality, it does not enforce it. The Information Technology Act, 2000 also does not prohibit companies from throttling their service in accordance with their business interests.

2. Shape of Internet Through Net Neutrality.

Net neutrality has shaped the internet in two fundamental ways-

One, web users are free to connect to whatever website or service they want. ISPs do not bother with what kind of content is flowing from their servers. This has allowed the internet to grow into a truly global network and has allowed people to freely express themselves. For example, you can criticize your ISP on a blog post and the ISP will not restrict access to that post for its other subscribers even though the post may harm its business.

But more importantly, net neutrality has enabled a level playing field on the internet. To start a website, you don't need lot of money or connections. Just host your website and you are good to go. If your service is good, it will find favour with web users. Unlike the cable TV where you have to forge alliances with cable connection providers to make sure that your channel reaches viewers, on internet you don't have to talk to ISPs to put your website online.

This has led to creation Google, Facebook, Twitter and countless other services. All of these services had very humble beginnings. They started as a basic websites with modest resources. But they succeeded because net neutrality allowed web users to access these websites in an easy and unhindered way.

3. Consequences of Internet without Net Neutrality.

If there is no net neutrality, ISPs will have the power to shape internet traffic so that they can derive extra benefit from it. For example, several ISPs believe that they should be allowed to charge companies for services like YouTube and Netflix because these services consume more bandwidth compared to a normal website. Basically, these ISPs want a share in the money that YouTube or Netflix make.

Without net neutrality, the internet as we know it will not exist. Instead of free access, there could be "package plans" for consumers. For example, if you pay Rs 500, you will only be able to access websites based in India. To access international websites, you may have to pay a more. Or maybe there can be different connection speed for different type of content, depending on how much you are paying for the service and what "add-on package" you have bought.

Lack of net neutrality, will also spell doom for innovation on the web. It is possible that ISPs will charge web companies to enable faster access to their websites. Those who don't pay may see that their websites will open slowly. This means bigger companies like Google will be able to pay more to make access to

Youtube or Google+ faster for web users but a startup that wants to create a different and better video hosting site may not be able to do that.

Instead of an open and free internet, without net neutrality we are likely to get a web that has silos in it and to enter each silo, you will have to pay some "tax" to ISPs.

4. Status of Net Neutrality in India

Legally, the concept of net neutrality doesn't exist in India. Sunil Abraham, director of Centre for internet and Society in Bangalore, says that The Telecom Regulatory Authority of India, TRAI, which regulates the telecom industry, has tried to come up with some rules regarding net neutrality several times. For example it invited comments on the concept of net neutrality from industry bodies and stakeholders in 2006. But no formal rules have been formed to uphold and enforce net neutrality.

However, despite lack of formal rules, ISPs in India mostly adhere to the principal of net neutrality. There have been some incidents where Indian ISPs have ignored net neutrality but these are few and far between. Essentially, on the recommendation of the Department of Telecom, the regulator is trying to determine whether internet service providers (ISPs) are discriminating in the distribution of bandwidth based on services used. Net Neutrality seeks an equal treatment of data and ISPs, owners of content networks have the power to control how that data is pushed to the end user.

So when you see a torrent website blocked, or a video buffering slowly, it is up to the service provider to determine the user's experience and allocate bandwidth for the user's content consumption. "Some content (like video) requires high bandwidth whereas some applications (like real-time gaming) have very stringent requirements. The exponential increase in Internet traffic and the evolving nature of the content that constitutes part of this traffic, can therefore lead to the overburdening of networks. As a result, TSPs (Telecom service providers) may not always be able to deliver an adequate level of QoS (Quality of Service) to their users," says TRAI.

Further, TRAI's consultation paper says, "Service providers generally use a range of techniques to manage the safety, security and efficiency of their networks. It is important to ensure that such techniques are not used by service providers in a discriminatory manner." For instance, when networks are overloaded, ISPs can decide which content stream to prioritise/throttle and which to withhold until the congestion is resolved.

However, the regulator specifies that any such Net Neutrality policy should not interfere with the ability of the ISP to manage their networks. "It is important to ensure that the end users who are affected by these practices have access to relevant information about the types of traffic shaping practices being followed by service providers and the reason for which they are being deployed," writes the regulator. Along with similar questions on appropriate internet traffic management, the regulator is also seeking to clearly define Net Neutrality in the Indian context. But, before it can do so, issues like traffic management need to be resolved.

5. Conclusion

Now, to determine acceptable or unacceptable traffic management practices, the regulator will first try and define what would constitute as "reasonable" traffic management practices. Another approach suggested by TRAI is to limit itself to a negative list of non-reasonable traffic management practices.

While TRAI may be seeking to check the discriminatory management of Internet traffic by ISPs and content service providers, it is important to know how the internet actually works. The internet is not controlled by a single service provider or various service providers individually, instead the internet is a series of networks interconnected to each other. So if you buffer a video on YouTube or send an email to a

friend, the information is broken down into different data packets, which travel alongside everyone else's data, given that the internet is also a shared medium.

The only part that ISPs such as an Airtel, Vodafone or any other provider controls is the last mile connectivity. So when talking about net neutrality, only this last mile connectivity should be considered. The content you request from the internet travels over multiple networks to get to you and broadband providers can only regulate this traffic when it reaches their network. It is this mile of network that is protected by the principles of Net Neutrality.

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